

Assessment of Daylight of Mid-Rise Office Buildings in Tropical Wet and Dry Climate of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Studies have shown that, there are limited studies of daylight in office buildings in Nigeria, and the few studies conducted on daylight in Nigerian office buildings did not cover all the seasonal changes of climatic conditions experienced in any of its climatic zone. The aim of the study was to investigate the daylight conditions of the two (2) mid-rise office buildings in Zaria and Kaduna metropolis which were in wet and dry climate of Nigeria. It was achieved by exploring the level of compliance with IEC requirements of office buildings in fulfilling the daylight autonomy (DA), useful daylight illuminance (UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀), and spatial daylight autonomy (sDA), based on international standards. The google sketch-up 2017 and Radiance simulation tool were used to evaluate the 13 offices in Ahmadu Bello University (ABU) senate building and Nagwamatse house. An exploratory design approach with the quantitative research strategy were employed in the study and the data generated was then analysed using statistical tools, such as bar charts and tables. The results showed that none of the daylight indicators met the standard's thresholds. It has also been observed that, building form, room orientation, window to wall ratio (WWR), building heights and roofing materials, influence the daylight requirements of an office building. The study concluded that, for mid rise office buildings in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria to meet the daylight requirements based on international standards, there is need to look at their building forms, orientations, WWR, and building heights.

Keywords: Daylight, Radiance, daylight autonomy, Useful daylight illuminance, Spatial daylight autonomy

1. Introduction

In developing countries like Nigeria, workers spend an average of 8 hours indoor in their offices daily especially those working in multi storey office buildings. This brought-about the need to have good indoor environmental offices, to prevent workers from building related sickness such as sick building syndrome. Daylight can be defined as the condition of architectural space where the optimum natural luminous is maintained. Xue, Mak, & Cheung (2014) and Magali, (2013)

viewed it as the people's satisfaction with the luminous environment. Daylighting Monitoring Protocols & Procedures for Buildings (1997) and Architectural Energy Corporation (2012) have shown that, daylight autonomy (DA), useful daylight illuminance (UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀), and spatial daylight autonomy (sDA) are the major indicators of daylight in Office buildings.

Boyce, (1998) has found out that, long exposure to electric-light bring about sickness and therefore working by daylight causes less stress and discomfort. Not much studies have been done on daylight of mid-rise office buildings in developing countries, especially in Africa, and the few studies conducted in Nigeria did not reflect the seasonal conditions experienced in the country. For example, Kadiri, Sells, Ukpomwan, & Salau, (2014) studied indoor environmental quality (IEQ) in multi storey office buildings and its implication on the health and safety of workers: evaluation of Lagos (tropical wet climate) state government administrative buildings in Nigeria, between February to April, 2012 while Ali, Martinson & Al-Maiyah, (2016) studied IEQ of learning environments in Bayero University, Kano (hot semi-arid climate) between 12th to 27th January, 2016. None of the aforementioned studies covered even the full wet or dry season of its climatic zone.

The aim of this study was to investigate conditions of the two (2) mid-rise office buildings in Zaria and Kaduna metropolis both in wet and dry climate of Nigeria. The objectives of the study were: to determine the level of compliance with daylight requirements of office buildings in wet and dry climate of Nigeria in fulfilling the daylight autonomy (DA), useful daylight illuminance (UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀) and Spatial daylight autonomy (sDA) based on Architectural Energy Corporation, AEC (2006), Society of Light and Lighting, SLL(2011) requirements. The evaluation studies were undertaken to answer the following:

- i. What is the level of compliance in daylighting requirements of office buildings in Nigeria in fulfilling the DA, performance metrics put forward by AEC and SLL?
- ii. To what extent does the UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀ comply with AEC and SLL?
- iii. To what extend does the sDA comply with AEC and SLL?

2. Literature Review

The effects of light on the building users could be categorised into two: visual effect, which enable people to see the world in order to interact with it, enhances human performance, health, wellbeing and productivity ((Edwards and Torcellini, 2002); and Non-visual effect, which impacts on human behaviours such as relieving seasonal depression (Rosen et al, 1990), increase of length and quality of sleep (Kareem, Nevin, & Lamis, 2016), reduction of anxiety and depression (Öztürk, Moreno & Lowden , 2017), reducing risk in Cardiovascular disease (Yamada., Hara, Shojima, Yamauchi & Kadowaki, 2015), to mention a few. The study dealt with the visual aspect of daylight which is important for its quality, spectral composition, and variability. Thus, the influence of daylight on the performance of tasks hinges on how the daylight is delivered.

A Mid Rise building in the study, meant any building with 4 to 12 floors, as classified by Alcox (2017) and Freedman (2009). The typology of office buildings varies from Engineering, Estate managers to Architecture point of views. Even in Architecture, there are various perspectives to office building classifications which include, Neufert (1980), who classified office buildings based on primary circulation as: Single banked office; and double banked office buildings. Peter (1965) classified office building based on the sizes, as: small office building, with 1858m² floor area; medium office building, with 1856m² to 9290m²; and large office building, with total floor area greater than 9290m². He also classified it based on access and services, as: Slab-type block; and the Core-type plan. In this study, office building is classified based on Space's ease of weather exchange, because this influences building daylight. Office building in this research was categorized into two: Single banked (Such as Senate Building, ABU Zaria), and double banked (such as Office of the New Nigeria Publishing Company Nagwamatse house, Kaduna).

There are a number of ways to measure daylight in an office building, but the most effective way was the Climate-Based Daylight Modelling (Salisu, 2013), which this study has adopted for daylighting. EnergyPlus, DesignBuilder and OpenStudio were some of the leading energy simulation tools in the world of building research technology. EnergyPlus was the most prominent and had the capabilities of BLAST and DOE-2, and extensively validated for over 20years as observed by Sousa, (date) and Crawley, Hand, Kummert, & Griffith, (2005). However,

Guglielmetti, Macumber, and Long (2011), noticed that, EnergyPlus and DOE-2 had clear limitations in their daylight simulation algorithms. Their engines could not accurately model daylight flux transfer into complex spaces, and could model only a limited number of daylight redirection technologies. It had also been observed that, design-Builder was not fast in analyzing a multiple simulation when compared to OpenStudio. OpenStudio was easier to visualize the building geometry and do some basic editing compared to other 2. It also had Radiance tool as plugin, which was the best for daylighting research. Through both PAT and the OpenStudio Analysis Spreadsheet, it increased the proficiency for users to run a large number of simulations. (Long, Ball, Fleming, & Macumber, 2014). Its users could import IDF file, edit surfaces and zones in the file and could set and change default constructions and assign daylighting controls (Rallapalli, 2010). For these reasons, Radiance in open-studio was chosen for this study.

3. Methodology

The study used simulation method to evaluate the daylight of the 13 number measured virtual offices of ABU senate building Zaria and Nagwamatse house Kaduna, in google sketch-up 2017 and Radiance in OpenStudio simulation tool, after validating the instrument and found it suitable for the research. An exploratory design approach using quantitative research strategy were employed and a convenience probability sampling technique was used in selecting the buildings. The criteria used in selection of these buildings was based on the difference in their Orientations, and building form. Other selection criteria include: number of storeys (mid-rise buildings); access to buildings; and HVAC system. Data was obtained from 13 offices of those buildings as shown in the table1.

Table 1. Study Population of offices in ABU Senate building and Nagwamatse office building.

S/No.	Building Name	Location	Building Form	Building Orientation	Floor level	Office Tag.	Ownership	
							Public	Private
1	ABU Senate building	Samaru, Zaria	Single banked	315 ⁰	1st	Academic Office	1	0
					3 rd	Computer Room	1	0
					4 th	Filing Room	1	0

					5 th	Record Office	1	0
					6 th	Secretary to Human Resources	1	0
					8 th	Office/Store	1	0
2	New Nigeria News Paper office Building	Nagwamut se House, Kaduna, metropolis	Double banked	90 ⁰	1 st	MD's office	0	1
					2 nd	Estate Surveyors	0	1
					3 rd	MD AA Usman & CO	0	1
					4 th	Mother Care, Gen. Office	0	1
					5 th	Drawing Office	0	1
					6 th	KD Consults	0	1
					8 th	Accounting Office	0	1

Source: Fieldwork, 2018

The procedure used in conducting the research was based on the: Daylighting Monitoring Protocols & Procedures for Buildings, 1997 and Monitoring Procedures for Assessment of Daylighting Performance of Buildings, 2001 (both published by the International Energy Agency IEA). Based on those documents the following steps were followed:

- Two office buildings were modelled in google sketch-up (including all properties of materials and ground reflectance) as shown in figure 1, and 2 below.

Figure 1. Simulated IEC of the Offices in Kaduna Nagwamatse house, (1-8th Floors).

Source: Field study, 2018

Figure 2. Simulated IEC of the Offices in ABU Senate building, Zaria.

- In order to simulate IEC components, such as daylight, IAQ and thermal comfort, EnergyPlus weather (EPW) was used as the type of weather file.
- Sketch-up plugging called OpenStudio was used to set weather files of Zaria and Kaduna from weather Analytic.
- Radiance measure for daylight, Space types, thermal zones, and construction materials were selected.
- Run period from January to December of 2018 was selected from Simulation settings
- Simulation button was pressed for the final analysis

4. Results and Data Analysis

The results of the evaluation studies with respect to the daylight autonomy DA, useful daylight illuminance UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀, and spatial daylight autonomy sDA, were presented on table 2a and 2b.

Table 2a. Simulation Results for the current conditions of ABU Senate builiding, Zaria

ABU SENATE BUILDING							
<i>DA= 52%, cDA = 0.73, UDI= 75%</i>							
<i>It is a</i>							
Latitude and longitude	11°09'03.11"N / 7°39'20.32"E, 11°09'01.98"N / 7°39'21.21"E, 11°09'02.95"N / 7°39'22.33"E, 11°09'03.96"N / 7°39'21.41"E						
		1 st floor	3 rd floor	4 th floor	5 th floor	6 th floor	8 th floor
		Academic office	Computer Room	Head Bursary Filing Room	Record Office	Secretary to Human Resource	Office/ Store

		NW	NW & NE	SW	NE	SW	NE
	Window to wall ratio	12.7%	27.5%	6.8%	9%	2.4%	10.7%
Daylight	DA (500)	30%	58%	46%	37%	35%	43%
	cDA (500)	0.48	0.64	0.68	0.54	0.53	0.58
	UDI (100-3000)	57%	55%	74%	57%	57%	57%
	sDA (8AM-5PM)	63%	97%	73%	77%	78%	90%

Source: field work, 2018

Table 2b. Simulation Results for the current conditions of Nagwamatse house, Kaduna

NAGWAMATSE HOUSE KADUNA								
DA= 46%, cDA = 0.71, UDI= 73%								
Latitude and longitude	10°31'55.94"N / 7°25'42.97"E, 10°31'55.42"N / 7°25'43.01"E, 10°31'55.421"N / 7°25'43.19"E, 10°31'54.46"N / 7°25'43.31"E, 10°31'54.47"N / 7°25'43.83"E, 10°31'55.91"N / 7°25'43.64"E							
		1 st floor	2 nd floor	3 rd floor	4 th floor	5 th floor	6 th floor	8 th floor
		MD's office	Estate surveyor	AA Usman & CO	Mother care Office	Drawing office	KD Consult	Accounting Office
		E	W	E	E	E	E	W
	Window to wall ratio	10%	11.8%	10.6%	11.8%	5%	10.8%	7.2%
Daylight	DA (500)	43%	44%	41%	44%	25%	43%	44%
	cDA (500)	0.58	0.58	0.56	0.58	0.44	0.57	0.66
	UDI (100-3000)	55%	55%	54%	55%	56%	54%	74%
	sDA (8AM-5PM)	91%	86%	84%	92%	59%	89%	66%

Source: field work, 2018

The analysis was done based on the benchmarks put forward by professional institutes and other determinants that were discovered in the studies. IESNA (2000) has recommended the use of 500 lux as illuminance task in office buildings, while the Architectural Energy Corporation, AEC (2006) put forward a DA threshold of 60% of the work plane illuminance (500lux in the case of offices); UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀ threshold of 80% of occupancy hours; sDA threshold of 75% (AEC, 2013).

The research was analysed based on the research questions raised earlier in this paper. The first question was that:

- i. What is the level of compliance in daylighting requirements of office buildings in Nigeria in fulfilling the DA, performance metrics put forward by AEC and SLL?

In this part, descriptive analysis was used to explore the level of compliance in daylighting requirements of ABU senate building and Nagwamatse house based on AEC and SLL.

From table 2a and 2b, it could be observed that, none of the 13 offices has complied with 60% DA, as specified in AEC (2013) and SLL, (2011) as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. Comparison of Daylight Autonomy of the 13 offices in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria. Source: Field work, 2018.

The next research question was:

- ii. To what extent does the $UDI_{100-3000}$ comply with AEC and SLL?

Descriptive analysis was also used to explore the level of compliance in daylighting requirements of ABU senate building and Nagwamatse house based on AEC and SLL.

Figure 4 shows that, none of the 13 offices has complied with 80% UDI, as specified in AEC (2013). It could also be observed that, offices in ABU senate buildings have higher DA and $UDI_{100-3000}$ values than those in Nagwamatse house, due to the effects of building form (ABU's is Single banked while Nagwamatse is double banked).

Figure 4. Comparison of Useful Daylight Autonomy of the 13 offices in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria. Source: Field work, 2018

It has been noticed that, *Computer Room* which was on the 3rd floor of ABU senate building, had 2 sources of daylight and had the highest window to wall ratio (WWR) of 27.5%, consequently had the highest DA value, as seen in figure 5.

Figure 5. Daylight sensor illuminance of computer room of ABU Zaria and Daylight sensor illuminance of Academic office ABU Zaria

Source: field work, 2018

It had also been observed that, *Office/Store* on the 8th floor of ABU senate building, with WWR greater than that of *Record office* on the 5th floor, had higher DA value than *Record office*, though they have the same orientation. While *Head Bursary Filing Room* on the 4th floor, with lower WWR than *Office/Store* on the 8th floor of ABU senate building, had higher DA value. *Accounting office* on the 8th floor of Nagwamatse house, oriented in west direction, and *Head Bursary Filing Room* on the 4th floor of ABU senate building with orientation of South-west, had the highest DA and UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀. These show that Orientation, WWR, and building heights have influence on the value of DA and UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀, on the mid-rise buildings. The next question was that:

- iii. To what extent does the sDA comply with AEC and SLL?

It could also be seen from table 2a and 2b that, 75% floor areas of 4 offices out of 6 selected from ABU senate building and 5 out of 7 offices from Nagwamatse house, have received at least 300 lux for at least 50% the annual occupied hours, which means that, 9 offices in the two mid-rise buildings received enough daylight during standard operating hours (8am to 5pm) as shown in figure 6. The figure 6 also shows that, Offices in Nagwamatse house have higher sDA values than

Figure 6. Comparison of Spatial Daylight Autonomy of the 13 offices in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria. Source: Field work, 2018

those in ABU senate building, this was due to the effects of orientation and WWR. Offices in Nagwamatse house were either facing east or west, and those that have met the standard have WWR equal or greater than 10. Those two offices that have not meet the 75% requirement was due to their low WWR values as seen on table 3. When sDA, and UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀ were considered together, it meant that, those 9 offices received more than the required daylight as they had not meet the required useful daylight illuminance, and therefore produced unwanted heat and glare in those offices.

5. Conclusion

This reserch have shown that, none of the daylight indicators met the standadard's thresholds of daylight requirements as specified by AEC (2006), SLL (2011) and ANSI/ASHRAE standards. It has also been observed that, building form, room orientation, WWR, and building heights influence the daylight of an office building.

In conclusion, for mid rise builddigs in tropical wet an dry climate of Nigeria to meet the daylight requirements based on the international standards, there is need to use appropriate office building typology, good orientations, understand the effects of building heights, and appropriate WWR

5.1 Recommendations

The Study recommends that: to design office building with adequate daylight, there is need to consider appropriate office building typology, good orientation, understand the effects of building heights in the micro-climate, the appropriate and WWR.

Moreover, government should have deliberate policy to establishing standards and guidelines in designing mid-rise office buildings in each climatic zone of Nigeria, based on determining the appropriate office building typology, orientation, and WWR.

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